

USING TRANSLATION STRATEGIES IN COMMUNICATIVE SITUATION

Khasanxonova Durdonakhon Juraxon kizi

(Student of SamSIFL)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7905618>

Annotation: In this article were discussed the relevance of the study is due to the need to clarify the strategies for the implementation of special translation in accordance with the communicative-functional approach to translation. The question of the dependence of the degree to which the content of the text is reproduced in translation depends on the characteristics of the communicative situation and the chosen strategy of translation is considered.

Key words: speech message, parameters, framework, information, translation, implementation

It seems that the solution of this problem is impossible without a preliminary definition of the basic concepts. The totality of these concepts will serve as a kind of theoretical basis for our further reasoning.

Among these concepts is primarily the concept of "communicative situation". In one of our previous works, we proposed the following definition of a communicative situation: "this is a fragment of reality, which is a systemic set of extralinguistic conditions for the implementation of objective activities of communicants, coordinated and agreed through their speech activity, during which a material product is created. - speech message" [Sdobnikov, 2015, p. 64]. This definition can be extended to a communicative situation using translation (hereinafter referred to as CST), bearing in mind a certain increase in the number of situation constituents.

In our opinion, all communicative situations with the use of translation can be divided into two types: situations in which translation is expected initially, that is, during the creation of the original (KSP-1), and situations in which translation is not initially expected, but is carried out. - occurs in connection with the emergence of a certain need for a potential consumer of translation (KSP-2). In the future, we will talk about communicative situations of the second type, in which the main provisions of the communicative-functional approach are implemented to the fullest extent possible.

These provisions make it necessary for the translator to analyze not only the linguistic characteristics of the translated text, but also the parameters of the communicative situation in which the translation is carried out. Among these parameters, we include, first of all, the needs of the recipient of the translation and the purpose of the translation determined by them, the nature of the subject activity carried out by the potential recipient of the TT, and the method of using the text of the translation. The analysis of these factors, which are exclusively extralinguistic in nature, allows the translator to choose exactly the translation strategy that makes it possible to ensure the achievement of the conscious goal of the translation.

In this case, we do not set ourselves the task of considering all possible approaches to determining the translation strategy. Our work proposes a general definition of a translation strategy: a translation strategy is a general program for the implementation of translation activities in a certain communicative situation of bilingual communication, determined by the specific features of this situation and the purpose of the translation, and, in turn, determining the nature of the professional behavior of the translator. within the framework of this

communicative situation [Sdobnikov, 2015, p. 135].

We also propose to distinguish three types of translation strategies.

(1) The strategy of communicatively equivalent translation is a program for the implementation of translation activities that provides for the implementation of the communicative intention of the author of the original in the form of creating a text in TL, potentially capable of providing a communicative impact on the recipient of the translation in accordance with the expectations of the original author and, accordingly, the interaction of multilingual communicants in the context of joint objective activity [Sdobnikov, 2015, p. 151]. The proposed definition of the strategy of communicatively equivalent translation has something in common with the definition of translation, well-known in translation science, proposed by A. D. Schweitzer [Schweitzer, 1988, p. 75].

(2) The strategy of tertiary translation is a general program for the implementation of translation activities aimed at creating a TL that satisfies the needs of the TL carrier, which plays a different communicative role than the participants in the primary communicative event in the FL culture, and pursues a goal different from the goal of the original author [Sdobnikov, 2015, p. 161-162]. The idea of a tertiary translation strategy is based on the idea of M. Ya. Zwillig about the existence of the so-called tertiary translation, or translation in the interests of third parties. "Translation here is not included in the chain of communication, but is an independent activity to extract information from the communication taking place between the partners in the interests of some outside observer who does not participate in the communication" [Ibid., p. 83]. A tertiary transfer is not intended to ensure that the impact of IT and AT on the respective recipients is equal.

(3) The redirection strategy is a general program for the implementation of translation activities aimed at creating a text in TL intended for a recipient that is different from the recipient of IT not only by their national and cultural affiliation, but also by their social characteristics [Sdobnikov, 2015, p. 170]. The term redirection was proposed by O. V. Petrova [Petrova, 2010]. She understands redirection as a set of actions of a translator in a situation "when the translation is intended for a target audience that differs from the target audience of the original not only in terms of its national and cultural characteristics, but also in terms of some social characteristics. These characteristics may include age, profession, educational level, place in a communication situation, etc." [Ibid., p. 20].

Below we will consider communicative situations of special translation, in which the strategy of tertiary translation is used. It is this strategy that presupposes certain content-semantic modifications of the text.

References:

1. Petrova, O. V. (2010). Pragmaticheskaya adaptatsiya i pereadresatsiya teksta pri perevode. In: Problemy perevoda i perevodovedeniya: sbornik nauchnykh trudov. Seriya «Yazyk. Kultura. Kommunikatsiya», 13. Nizhniy Novgorod NGLU im. N. A. Dobrolyubova. 17—23. (In Russ.).
2. Sdobnikov, V. V. (2015). Perevod i kommunikativnaya situatsiya: monografiya. Moskva: Flinta: Nauka. (In Russ.).
3. Shveytser, A. D. (1988). Teoriya perevoda: status, problemy, aspekty. Moskva: Nauka. (In Russ.).

4. Даминов Н. К. СИНХРОН ТАРЖИМАНИНГ АСОСИЙ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //PEDAGOGIK ISLOHOTLAR VA ULARNING YECHIMLARI. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 66-69.
5. Кулдошов У. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида конверсивлик ва антонимлик ҳодисаси //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 3 (80). – С. 67-73.
6. Daminov N. K. SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION INTERPRETING AS A MODERN TYPE OF TRANSLATION //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 77-81.
7. Daminov N. SCIENTIFIC VARIETIES OF TRANSLATION STRATEGIES //Конференция: Союз Науки и Образования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 25-28.
8. Kudratovich D. N. SOME VIEWS ABOUT TRANSLATION STRATEGY //International Congress on Models and methods in Modern Investigations. – 2023. – С. 15-17.
9. Kasimova A. N., Nurullayeva D. S. H. NEOLOGISMS IN MODERN ENGLISH AND THEIR TRENDS IN WORD FORMATION (BASED ON TEXTS IN THE MEDIA) //Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 130-133.
10. Sukhrobovna N. T. AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARDA MATNLARNING GRAMMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – Т. 24. – С. 1087-1090.
11. Сафаров Ш. Тил бирлиги ва воқелик муносабати //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 2 (79). – С. 5-8.